

Constructing Entrepreneurial Identity in Entrepreneurship Education

Author's Details:

Saba Fazal Firdousi^{1*} Prof. Dr. Cai Li^{2*} Hasnain Javed^{3*} Majid Murad^{4*}
(1)(2)(3)(4) Jiangsu University, School of Management, Zhenjiang, P.R. China, 212013.

Correspondence Author: Saba Fazal Firdousi

Abstract

While expanding interest for pioneering ability has prompted steady development in business enterprise instruction, few projects give vigorous results, for example, genuine new pursuits or innovative conduct in genuine settings. This is because of a hole in our hypothetical comprehension of the stuff to end up enterprising. Research recommends that past procuring information and the ability to act innovatively, enterprising adapting likewise includes the improvement of a pioneering character. However most records of business enterprise instruction do exclude this idea. We investigate enterprising personality and how it is built inside a business instruction.

Interfacing innovative learning hypothesis with writing on character, we built up a lot of classes tending to the development of a pioneering personality. For a situation learn at a European specialized college, we utilized these classes to test and dissect account information created as understudies made new pursuits. The outcomes bolster our supposition that, with regards to another endeavor creation program, understudies experience moves that lead to the improvement of innovative personality. In light of these discoveries, we contend that on the off chance that the instructive goal is learning for the act of business, at that point personality development should be viewed as significant an objective as the improvement of information and ability

Keywords: entrepreneurial identity, entrepreneurial education, innovation, creativity

1. Introduction

Enterprise has for quite some time been recognized as a factor in financial thriving (see for instance Baumol, 1986; Baumol, Litan, and Schramm, 2007), and subsequently approach creators and specialists progressively call upon the requirement for innovative fitness to drive development in their districts (OECD, 2011; World Economic Forum, 2011). Accentuation on growing new business people that can convey this competency is set apart by the proceeded with the development of pioneering instruction programs (Finkle and Deeds, 2001; Katz, 2003; McMullan and Long, 1987; Solomon, 2007). In any case, not all prompt the improvement of innovatively acting people or the formation of new firms (Gruber, 2007; Honig and Samuelsson, 2012; Karlsson and Honig, 2007). While it is generally recognized that higher pioneering training ought to incorporate experiential instructional method so as to improve learning and creative limit (Barrett and Peterson, 2000; Collins, Smith, and Hannon, 2006; Honig, 2004; Johannisson, Landstrom, & Rosenberg, 1998; Lundstrom & Stevenson,

¹ Authors Note: Saba Fazal Firdousi is currently enrolled as PhD Candidate for Management and Engineering Sciences in School of Management at Jiangsu University, Zhenjiang, China. Email ID:sabafazalfirdousi@gmail.com

² Authors Note: Dr Cai Li is currently serving as an Associate Professor in School of Management, Jiangsu University, Zhenjiang, China. She is also the corresponding author for this paper. Email ID: gsxxml@yahoo.cn

³ Authors Note: Hasnain Javed is currently enrolled as PhD Candidate for Management and Engineering Sciences in School of Management at Jiangsu University, Zhenjiang, China. He is also the corresponding author for this paper. Email ID:hassnain.javed@hotmail.com

⁴ Authors Note: Majid Murad is currently enrolled as PhD Candidate for Management and Engineering Sciences in School of Management at Jiangsu University, Zhenjiang, China.

2002; Pittaway & Cope, 2007; Vinton & Alcock, 2004; Yballe & O'Connor 2000), there are still various ways to deliver entrepreneurship education.

Shifting instructive methodologies recognize training directed about, in, for, or through business enterprise (Chang and Rieple, 2013; Co and Mitchell, 2006; Heinonen and Poikkijoki, 2006; Hytti and O'Gorman 2004; Kirby, 2004; Mwasalwiba, 2010; Pittaway and Edwards, 2012). Ollila and Williams Middleton (2011) contend that the 'about' and 'in' ways to deal with business enterprise training are inadequate when endeavoring to animate innovative conduct and grow new pursuits. They contend that understudies need to do the genuine work of making another endeavor so as to create innovative competency. Of the four fundamental sorts of enterprise training portrayed above, just the last mentioned ('through') fuses commitment in real adventure creation.

Among the first to depict ways to deal with learning through business, Gibb (1996) recognized an ambitious showing approach as fundamental for interfacing calculated information to a scope of enterprising practices. Following Gibb, specific methodologies have been created to encourage learning through commitment in the act of business enterprise (see for instance Heinonen, 2007; Heinonen and Poikkijoki, 2006). Ollila and Williams Middleton (2011) present an endeavor creation approach that coordinates brooding of feasible thoughts into the instructive procedure. The methodology enables understudies to "try things out" by including them in genuine innovative and business exercises as the main entertainers (the enterprising group). This encourages various key learning viewpoints distinguished by others: learning by doing, reflection upon moves made (Cope, 2003; Cope and Watts, 2000), improvement of basic leadership rationales (Chandler, DeTienne, McKelvie, and Mumford, 2011; Sarasvathy, 2001) and prioritization of exercises, all with the purpose of effectively making new pursuits. Researchers even contend that so as to animate pioneering conduct, instruction must go past reenacting it by including genuine endeavor creation as a major aspect of the formal educational program (Ollila and Williams Middleton, 2011; Williams Middleton and Donnellon, 2014). At the point when understudies go about as business people over the span of their training, e doing the assignments of making another endeavor e it is inescapable that they take on this new personality somewhat. Innovative learning researchers have talked about the significance of oneself in learning and some have examined personality.

Specialists concentrating the individuals who figure out how to be enterprising by beginning and dealing with an endeavor propose that this competency is far more extensive than abilities and information (see, for instance, Breslin and Jones, 2012; Harrison and Leitch, 2011; Karatas, Ozkan, 2011; Morris, Kuratko, Schindehutte, and Spivack, 2012; Pittaway and Thorpe, 2012; Rae, 2004, 2005, 2006). As Obrecht (2004) contends, so as to act innovatively, people need a lot of abilities which are close to home, hierarchical and cultural. In this way, parts impacting enterprising capacity incorporate character and learning just like systems, authenticity and area (Obrecht, 2011). Pioneering learning researchers (Hytti, 2003; Pittaway and Thorpe, 2012; Rae, 2006) find that learning in this setting prompts thought of 'whom I need to be' and development of a personality that authorizes this desire.

In his work, David Rae contends that enterprising learning isn't just review, yet additionally joins the current experience and future reasoning and claims that "in innovative getting the hang of, knowing, acting and seeming well and good are interconnected" (Rae, 2000, pg. 151). Others have expounded on this contention, finding that work to create enterprising personality includes inner self-reflection, yet in addition social commitment e through talk and activity (Radu Lefebvre and Redien-Collot, 2013; Rigg and O'Dwyer, 2012; Watson, 2009). However, when connecting socially, especially with built-up social gatherings, people attempting to assume the personality of business visionary are regularly tested with how this new character fits with existing personalities and jobs (Williams Middleton, 2013).

These records of the innovative learning procedure are a practically indistinguishable match with the developing hypothesis of character development in writing on work job advances, in which case people are found to make, test, and incorporate temporary selves in respect to a job they have or look for (Ibarra, 1999). The authoritative

hypothesis also gives a solid case to the significance of character at both the individual and hierarchical levels (Ashforth and Mael, 1989; DeRue, Scott and Ashford, 2010; Gioia, Price, Hamilton and Thomas, 2010; Lounsbury and Glynn, 2001; Navis and Glynn, 2011). For instance, at the individual level, Sveningsson and Alvesson (2003) underscore that character is integral to significance, inspiration, basic leadership, and different exercises that can be viewed as basic for enterprising activity. At the firm level, Glynn and her partners have done various investigations of the procedure and impacts of character work opposite its outer partners.

Speculations of individual and hierarchical changes, alongside those with respect to enterprising adapting, consequently perceive that personality development is a significant piece of making business visionaries (Wigren, 2003). Be that as it may, neither the writing on enterprising hypothesis nor on business training has fundamentally tended to the procedure of personality development throughout instruction nor how pioneering character 'work' might be coordinated with the individual aptitude and information advancement. We point here to fill this hole by tending to the accompanying inquiries: how is an enterprising character built through the procedure of new pursuit creation; and by what method can business enterprise training foster personality advancement.

Our article includes a hypothetical system created from the writing on pioneering personality development just as an exact use of this structure to story information gathered from an enterprise instruction that uses the "learning 'through' approach." Our Methodology Section portrays the specific circumstance, strategy and discoveries of our contextual investigation and is then trailed by a dialog and ends segment.

The primary hypothetical commitment of this article is to the field of enterprise instruction. We expand on hypotheses about the pioneering character to investigate what an activity based instruction can do to encourage adventure creation as well as enterprising personality development. In this manner, the article associates the different fields of innovative learning and business enterprise instruction. For all intents and purposes, we trust our discoveries will encourage the instructive advancements that will create more prominent pioneering skills and invigorate increasingly enterprising conduct and new pursuit creation.

Entrepreneurial identity construction

We led a writing search in the database Scopus, utilizing two inquiry terms: character and enterprise. The hunt was restricted to peer-checked on diary articles in sociology productions up to a year, finishing 2012, bringing about 160 distributions. The dominant part was distributed inside the most recent two decades (with one exemption), with the greater part of the articles distributed somewhere in the range of 2008 and 2012.

It ended up clear through our audit that a significant part of the writing did not explicitly address how pioneering personality is built, yet rather talked about depiction of the individual character, or enterprising personality related to a firm, industry or country. Endless supply of every one of the 160 articles, we chose 24 that were pertinent to our enthusiasm for the procedures of pioneering character development. Through a more profound examination, we recognized four fundamental subjects as adding to this marvel. Table 1 shows the articles sorted out as per four fundamental subjects. Next, we examine the topics in detail, including introducing proposals from the writing towards utilization of personality development in instruction.

Socialization and collectivity

One subject coming from the writing is that pioneering character results from a person's socialization and can be a piece of an aggregate personality. Proficient character creates in a social setting and social gatherings that people identify with expertly, for instance through expert standards. Training adds to an aggregate personality improvement through formation of a mentality during the whole tutoring procedure, both as far as subject substance and learning style/strategy. For instance, in an investigation looking at understudies' qualities, Aaltio (2008) contends that the instructive procedure by which character is developed is significant, yet similarly applicable is its substance. As indicated by Aaltio, the utilization of stories, the incitement of implicit

information of the members, aggregate sharing of involvement and pondering these encounters all help personality building and in this way ought to be a piece of the board training planning to meet new monetary conditions.

Along a similar line of thinking, Shepherd and Haynie (2009a) talk about the test business people face in adjusting between satisfying a requirement for peculiarity and having a feeling of having a place altogether with keeping up mental wellbeing (as studies demonstrate that people search out both a feeling of self through uniqueness, yet in addition have a mental need of having a place). The creators contend that for business visionaries, the hazard is an awkwardness towards peculiarity is extraordinary, as this identifies with the pioneering job related to another endeavor, which must be particular. The creators recommend that the uniqueness predisposition may be adjusted through small scale characters partner with different zones of the person's life to encourage a feeling of having a place.

Strategic positioning

The second subject we recognized is the vital situating that the individual attempts as he/she guarantees the authoritative job of a business visionary. For business enterprise understudies making new pursuits, the personality of business visionary creates

Table 1
Summary of selected literature.

Identity construction themes	References
Socialization and collectivity	Aaltio (2008) Chand and Misra (2009) Falck, Heblich and Luedermann (2010) Obschonka, Goethner, Silbereisen, and Cantner (2012) Rigg and O'Dwyer (2012) Shepherd and Haynie (2009a, 2009b) Wry, Lounsbury, and Glynn (2011)
Strategic positioning	Essers and Benschop (2007) Hytti (2005) Jones and Spicer (2005) Madsen, Neergaard, and Ullhøi (2008) Nadin (2007)
Visual and oral symbols	Anderson and Warren (2011) Boje and Smith (2010) Clarke (2011) Down and Warren (2008) Smith (2011)
Storytelling	Fletcher and Watson (2007) Haynie and Shepherd (2011) Harmeling (2011) Jain, George, and Maltarich (2009) Johansson (2004) Rae (2005) Steyaert (2007)

after some time, as does the character of the firm. Moves must be made to authentic the new pursuit among different partners and in the commercial center, and these activities likewise shape the advancing character of the pioneering people and their developing associations. Intentionally or not, these activities speak to a vital situating of the self in the job (Jones and Spicer, 2005).

Rigg and O'Dwyer (2012) contend that the enterprising part of human personality is emanant and social and it is created through discourse with family, clients, workers, providers, contenders and others. They represent how

coach arranges in the instruction program can invigorate the hopeful business visionaries' realizing 'how to be,' accordingly empowering procurement of status and personality. The creators contend that people gain proficiency with the most when acting at the 'edge of nature.' The limit of the 'recognizable' can be reached out through the social cooperation with guide systems, including verbal, yet non-verbal commitments also.

Visual and oral symbols

How do business people influence pertinent partners to turn out to be a piece of their endeavor in spite of an absence of substantial proof of capability? In endeavoring to legitimize their endeavor and persuade others regarding the practicality of their innovative thought, business visionaries rely on their own viability of emblematically utilizing discourse and visual introduction.

Visual and oral images are likewise observed as adding to pioneering personality (Boje and Smith, 2010; Clarke, 2011; Down and Warren, 2008; Smith, 2011). Clarke (2011) exhibits how business people utilize visual images to introduce a fitting scene to partners, make proficient personality and underline control/direct feelings. Visual images utilized include: setting e office furniture, space and outside environment; props e pictures/works of art, showcases of models, surrounded licenses/authentic archives; dress e formal or casual, to affect on the crowd; expressiveness e outwardly passed on feelings or musings through body or facial developments.

Oral images like prosaisms e verbose methods by which to investigate the potential outcomes of joining new or generally new encounters into the person's ontological account e are additionally used to verify innovative self-personality (Down and Warren, 2008). The hackneyed language, including components, for example, chance, desire, development and control, is seen to conceivably bring out clear symbolism all the more securely.

Storytelling

Research on innovative personality underlines narrating as a significant piece of character development (see, for example, Fletcher and Watson, 2007; Harmeling, 2011; Hytti, 2005; Johansson, 2004; Rae, 2005; Steyaert, 2007). Harmeling (2011) offers a conceptualization of the pioneering character development process as re-storying, in which "people embrace to create, keep up and display both individual and social personalities." (pg. 746). She contends that business enterprise instruction can be a 'character workspace' where people can pick up information, yet encounters including the advancement of self-account. Through examining the differentiating biographies of two business visionaries, Johansson (2004) contends that narrating is utilized to outline apparent and ordered 'windows of chances' including discoursed, which the business visionary has both with himself and with others. Rigg and O'Dwyer (2012) delineate manners by which the business visionary arranges discoursed and stories in association with basic others to legitimize the personality being developed. It is through such narrating, and the related arranging and cooperation with others, that the business person shows enterprising knowledge picked up.

Summarizing the themes

When inspecting writing tending to procedures of pioneering character development, the first and maybe evident perception is that personality development occurs after some time (Falck et al., 2010), as people catch both inside and remotely with the new personality. Inside, business visionaries, similar to all people, battle to discover the harmony between their requirements for having a place and qualification (Madsen et al., 2008; Nadin, 2007; Rigg and O'Dwyer, 2012; Shepherd and Haynie, 2009a). They additionally battle to accommodate the individual and social pressures that originate from having different "miniaturized scale characters" got from their having a place with various social groupings (family, religion, ethnicity, sex, race, and so forth) (Chand and Misra, 2009; Essers and Benschop, 2007; Hytti, 2005; Obschonka et al., 2012; Rigg and O'Dwyer 2012).

Pioneering personality is built through the commitment and impact of friends (Falck et al., 2010; Obschonka et al., 2012). Business people consult with basic others to pick up authenticity (Clarke, 2011; Essers and

Benschop, 2007; Nadin, 2007; Wry et al., 2011) as a feature of a socialization procedure and acceptance into an aggregate character. The most ordinarily examined methods for building an innovative character is through narrating and account (Anderson and Warren, 2011; Boje and Smith, 2010; Down and Warren, 2008; Fletcher and Watson, 2007; Johansson, 2004; Smith, 2011; Steyaert, 2007; Wry et al., 2011). Narrating and story are characteristic and significant methods for use in business enterprise training, as they invigorate enunciation of unsaid learning from understudies and different members. This verbal cooperation and utilization of account take into account aggregate sharing of understanding and reflection on encounters. These help the development of an innovative personality and will be talked about further in the last area.

Models from the articles additionally point to the connection between the procedures of innovative character development at both the individual and firm levels. Boje and Smith (2010) found that the organizations of businesspeople co-produced the characters of their pioneering pioneers by blending the corporate purposefulness of the pictures and accounts with pieces of direct talk. The connection between the individual and the firm is likewise talked about in Rae's (2005) model for innovative realizing, which incorporates the person's close to home and social development, logical learning and arranged venture. Individual and social rise originate from finding out about oneself which educates the improvement and testing regarding enterprising personality. The logical learning and arranged undertaking proceed with the account advancement of character, yet grows to incorporate the narrative of the firm, not simply the business person.

These articles speak to the distributed learning about how innovative character is built and give a profitable establishment to guessing about for enterprising personality work that can create and ought to be cultivated inside business training. We utilize the hypothetical structure to investigate enterprising personality development inside an activity based, adventure creation program, seen as using a learning 'through' business enterprise approach.

Methodology

The contextual analysis depends on insider activity to examine standards, which take into account the age of new logical learning through the use of setting based experiences while at the same time empowering consistent and extra abilities inside the setting under scrutiny. First we will present the experimental setting of the contextual investigation so as to qualify the setting as illustrative of a learning 'through' way to deal with business enterprise instruction. At that point we present the techniques utilized for accumulation and examination of information with respect to the hypothetical structure created from writing.

Setting --- a venture creation education

The examination researches an endeavor creation program, in presence since 1997, at a specialized college in Europe. The program embodies a learning 'through' way to deal with business enterprise training. The two-year bosses program, averaging 35 understudies for every partner, gives training and direction, and connects with understudies in genuine endeavor creation during the subsequent year, with the goal to consolidate the endeavor if conceivable. The program works together with an uncommonly planned pre-incubator, characterized as a beginning time business hatchery, in charge of enrolling and authoritatively verifying endeavor thoughts for the program just as furnishing seed-financing combined with the board support, and innovative job sets including tutors, analysts, consultants, and so on. For every companion, understudies are framed into groups of 2e3 and distributed an endeavor thought. Should adventures delineate market reasonability, they are fused at the end (or at some point from that point) of the training. Understudies [graduates] proceeding with the fused endeavor after fruition of the training have both a value offer and business position. As instructors at the school, we approach an exact setting considered suitable for investigating character development.

New venture creation and entrepreneurial behavior outcomes

This program has encountered impressive achievement in delivering innovative entertainers; results that help our conviction that clarifications past expertise and information should likewise be considered on the off chance that we are to see how to create a more extensive arrangement of skills. In the fourteen years of its reality through 2011, an aggregate of 304 alumni has instructed from the program. A sum of 148 thoughts was hatched over the span of the instruction. As of part of the arrangement, aggregate of 50 organizations had been joined, of which 40 were still in presence, speaking to an 80% survival pace of consolidated endeavors.

Notwithstanding the proportion of new pursuit creation, the program additionally exhibits advancement of innovative conduct (Lackeus, 2013). Graduated class is observed to rehearse enterprise in a wide range of limits. For instance, in about the majority of the 50 fused endeavors, in any event one of the understudies required during the instructive period turned into an originator representative in the endeavor when fused. Also, various different organizations have been established by graduated class after graduation from the program. While this is progressively hard to evaluate in view of the difficulties of following graduated class after some time, conspicuous models have emerged, including a graduated class organization as of late recorded as one of the 33 most sizzling youthful specialized organizations in the nation in 2012, and another graduated class, the CEO of an autonomously shaped organization, recorded as the 2012 'Super-ability of the Year', in the country's driving business diary. At last, in an ongoing graduated class overview, most of respondents (all-out 121, in this manner speaking to 40% of the whole graduated class base) distinguished themselves as working in an enterprising limit. 64.3% of respondents concurred or emphatically concurred that they had the learning, aptitude and experience required to begin another business, and 88.4% concurred or unequivocally concurred that they had the information, expertise and experience required to begin another activity inside a current association. Obviously, an innovative group character has been encouraged, as have singular personalities. Yet, what is the procedure by which these are built?

Data collection and analysis

Experimental information is routinely created in this program as a major aspect of the instructive undertaking and was accessible to be examined and dissected to investigate the way toward developing a pioneering personality. Information originates from a few sources and collaborations that happen as a piece of the instructive plan, including understudy diary passages, organized workforce understudy talks, organized staff understudy group talks, and questioning occasions. With the end goal of this article, information was chosen from sources gathered somewhere in the range of 2005 and 2013.

In the investigation for this paper, the hypothetical system of enterprising personality development was utilized, for example information was specifically coded to pick up knowledge into components of socialization and collectivity, vital situating, visual and oral images just as narrating that are normally happening in an activity based business enterprise training. The methodology of the examination pursued two principle ventures: in the underlying period of investigation, the creators experienced the transcripts and utilized open coding to discover portions where the character was at issue for further examination as endorsed by Strauss and Corbin (1990). In the subsequent stage of the examination, the records were organized into the four subjects of the hypothetical system in a procedure of hub coding (Strauss and Corbin, 1990). See Table 2. The investigation included two of the creators of this paper.

Identifying entrepreneurial identity construction themes in an educational setting

The selections give delineations of innovative character development. Inside the activity based innovative training, understudies realize which exercises are valued and connected with a 'pioneering' character through input from companions and different partners. The language understudies' utilization and the manner in which they associate with their partners embody stories, platitudes and images of enterprise, the pioneering job, the innovative group, and the pioneering adventure. They utilize these phonetic ways to develop a personality for themselves, which they would then be able to consult with others so as to assemble authenticity and

acknowledgment in the job they hope for. In each extract, understudies produce visual pictures and stories as a component of their procedure of making the endeavor.

Extract 1, taken from an understudy diary section, represents how an understudy sees his job in the enterprising group and how this movement dependent on input from companions.

Extract 1 (understudy diary section): "... we have been talking inside the gathering about our jobs and how we are seen by the others. This is something that I acknowledge, particularly since I get the opportunity to reflect over what my gathering is enlightening me and afterward think regarding it in real life as it were. One solid case of this is the means by which I act during gatherings. I, for the most part, take a ton of room and gab and once in a while, I have an inclination that I should make a stride back and let the others talk more. In any case, my gathering individuals have now revealed to me that they value that I can lead the pack in gatherings or in exchanges. Today, Friday, we had a gathering with [Henry] and after this gathering my gathering individuals revealed to me that I was generally excellent during this gathering by bringing up some significant issues and perspectives and that they valued that I was not "apprehensive" of taking the discourse with specialists inside their very own fields. This was an awesome encounter for me and now I realize that this side is refreshing despite the fact that I should consider when it is reasonable to utilize it more and when it is appropriate to utilize it less."

Extract 1 is a case of pioneering character development through visual and oral images (Boje and Smith, 2010) in the manner in which the understudy is acting by 'taking a great deal of room' when addressing key partners and on basic gatherings, and after that socially verified by criticism from the group. Along these lines, the understudy is additionally attempting to both increase and after that, keep up authenticity in the ideal job of 'business person' (Somers, 1994; Williams Middleton, 2013).

In Excerpt 2, taken from an understudy workforce advancement talk halfway through the endeavor creation process, the understudy portrays how he and his partners make an account of the supervisory crew, and after that, position themselves with respect to other key partners. In any case, they don't really acknowledge the personality of the supervisory crew until they have occupied with specific exercises.

Portion 2 (personnel understudy talk, mid-term): "... it's an issue of how we, how we really utilized our situation as the supervisory crew ... the two, three a week ago of the venture resembled, we began to be the genuine supervisory group. We began to look into things, we began to really call individuals, and paint our very own image of how the world looks, and not the specialists' perspective on it. And afterward when we exhibited it at the executive gathering, they were really shocked, similar to: 'gracious!' And as [my teammate] stated, one of the thought suppliers really said that: 'perhaps, that is really the world that you should go in. However the exploration world is very different.' And [we thought], all right, yet we're not going to do any business in the examination world. Also, I feel like, OK, we're the supervisory group. I concur with [my teammate], we were from the earliest starting point. ... But on the other hand we weren't the supervisory crew since we didn't act [as] the supervisory group until we began to fundamentally really look and paint our own image and how it was out there."

Portion 2 shows how understudies use discourse and narrating to developing a way of life as an enterprising group. Building the way of life as the supervisory group of the enterprising firm is empowered through narrating of activities as an approach to legitimize the personality, first toward basic partners of the endeavor, in the manner in which that the business choices are exhibited, and afterward again in the retelling of the story to an employee as outline of accomplished and approved job of 'supervisory group', demonstrating how guides are utilized as methods towards character development (Rigg and O'Dwyer, 2012).

Portion 3 is taken from a staff discourse with an enterprising group, halfway through the endeavor creation process in training. The understudy utilizes imagery to convey the change procedure he has experienced, and how that changes the manner in which he introduces himself to his companions outside the training.

Table 2
Axial coding of the descriptive excerpts.

Identity construction themes	Excerpts
Socialization and collectivity	4, 5
Strategic positioning	1, 2, 3, 5
Visual and oral symbols	1, 3, 4
Storytelling	2, 3

Selection 3 (staff understudy group talk, part of the bargain): "the start, you claimed to be a business visionary, or you professed to be a proprietor of a venture. You were telling [your friends] various stuff. What's more, presently, you can really put it down in a few words and state: 'this is our specialty,' and they like: 'goodness.' Furthermore, that says a great deal on the grounds that before all else it was: 'this is the thing that we have, and this is what we will do,' and I feel more like a business person now than I completed 4 months prior. I feel like all right; presently, I can really represent the words, pretty much. ... Sometimes you need to turn at the corner, and afterward you realize you've changed, yet now and again it resembles the world goes this way (indicating moving movements), and out of the blue you're here and you realize that you turned a corner, yet you didn't know about that when you did it, and when you think back [you see that] you did. So it feels more like a procedure of that sort than an extreme change."

Like passage 2, portion 3 shows how understudies use narrating with their job set (Harmeling, 2011; Navis and Glynn, 2011; Nielsen and Lassen, 2012; Smith, 2011), which may incorporate amazing entertainers, to represent and arrange a pioneering personality (Williams Middleton, 2013), frequently by building up and testing temporary characters (Ibarra, 1999) through the emanant procedure of the endeavor being shaped. What's more, there is a helpful differentiation that can be made between the developing ability that happens because of the unique circumstance and difficulties, contrasted with the purposeful moves an understudy makes (or is provoked to take by the instruction) to build a pioneering personality. Portion 3 begins demonstrating the last mentioned, yet in addition at last likewise demonstrates the inferred competency advancement the understudy accomplishes through the procedure of association with the partners.

In Excerpt 4, taken from an understudy diary section, an understudy reflects upon intuitive workshops he/she includes went to inside the instructive condition where he/she was presented to practicing entrepreneurs.

Extract 4 (understudy diary section): "This week I have gone to three introductions where business visionaries recount to an incredible account. The first was with [Andy] and he discussed his adventure with a ton of spotlight on the significant elements with regards to having an effective endeavor. I observed his introduction to be extremely useful such that it progressed toward becoming more clear to me what job the various people should have in an endeavor. I especially preferred the manner in which he portrayed the business people similar to the ones in the driver seat, adding to the undertaking with drive and excitement. It sort of helped me to much more, if conceivable, attempt to persuade our thought suppliers that we have the drive and capacity to make this an effective endeavor. From the other two introductions, [Olle and Martha], I attempted to pay heed to what words and articulations that grabbed my eye with the end goal for me to have the option to sell myself and our thought. I attempted to consider this during the blend session ... "

Selection 4 additionally embodies how understudies use good examples to help create temporary characters for the job 'business person.' The understudies embrace referent power (Martin, 1978), expanding on the view of a 'built-up business visionary,' and receive words and articulations as the prosaisms (Down and Warren, 2008) so as to help build up a pioneering personality.

Portion 5 gives a case of a socialization procedure, where John's exercises are deciphered through his partners so as to shape their very own personalities and that of their developing endeavor.

Passage 5 (questioning occasion): "[John] was the center main thrust behind Project Delta e there was no doubt of his enterprising drive and power for the movement of the task. He was very skilled in systems administration and uniting key faculty and truly understanding the requirements of causing the business to develop. In any case, he was so made up for a lost time in driving the task that it was devouring him. He wound up expanding dependent on his partners, [Mary and Steve], to stay his exercises, help him catch and compose in composed and illustrative structure the basic needs, following stages, and longer-term destinations of the task. We had incalculable talks through the course of the training, both one-on-one and in a gathering about how to endeavor to adjust exercises, permit time for reflection and rundown while simultaneously expanding proficiency and viability of the undertaking and instructive exercises."

For certain understudies, it is hard to isolate the development of the innovative job and the improvement of the firm. John, in passage 5, is reliant upon his partners to help structure how he can successfully add to the developing firm. Appointment and association of errands conceivably tumble to various entertainers in the enterprising group, making a potential strain between the individual and aggregate character. This additionally delineates the test of adjusting between the individual innovative character and the advancement of the endeavor, as talked about by Shepherd and Haynie (Shepherd and Haynie, 2009a, 2009b).

Discussion and conclusion

This article tries to investigate how the procedure of innovative character development advances in and can be encouraged through an activity based business instruction approach. We contend that the development of an innovative personality is as basic a piece of creating enterprising competency as are aptitudes and information advancement, especially if the instructive target is learning for the act of business.

Plainly setting is a significant supporter of innovative character, as it gives the meaningful gestures that impact the person's feeling of having a place or potentially separation from their social gatherings. Setting can likewise make social clashes as people advance toward the new character. Research reports that character clashes related to business happen in certain societies and social gatherings. Hence there might be a part of understudies that battle more around their creating innovative personality inside the instructive setting. The understudies enter the training within any event one notable character (Stryker and Serpe, 1982), and likely fluctuate in how much their personalities are molded by their own, mental make-up or their social affiliations (Jain et al., 2009; Obschonka et al., 2012). Every individual will probably go up against their very own interior exchange about how the innovative personality fits with their social gatherings' desires and requests. What's more, each should participate in dealings about the authenticity of his/her enterprising personality with these social gatherings, and others.

A pioneering character is primarily related to an expert job e that of the originator of a new business e but at the same time is affected by social standards about the exemplification of the job. In this manner, the development of the pioneering character frequently creates through connection with basic partners who can verify or refute authenticity claims (Williams Middleton, 2013). Notwithstanding when concentrating on the formation of the endeavor's character, the significance of account and narrating in one's own personality work is unequivocally obvious for the situation study.

In business instruction, there is potential for structure understudy familiarity with how certain scenes are significant from a character development point of view. Understudies could figure out how to perceive and use basic episodes/occasions to their motivation, for instance as images to be joined into the narrating and arranged stories used to pick up authenticity. Assignments that expect understudy to think about, investigate, and examine their advancing characters, gathering and individual clashes, give space to them to utilize these encounters for their own learning (Aaltio, 2008; Harmeling, 2011; Rae, 2005). We recommend that instructive encounters, which point out basic occurrences, mark them as sensible and give chances to trying and acting business visionaries to consider, plan for, and consult around such encounters can build capacity to develop a pioneering personality.

Note that our experimental discoveries come from a setting with a learning 'through' structure, however not a particular plan situated towards enterprising personality development. All things considered, the discoveries show that the methods and requirement for pioneering character development create as a major aspect of the commitment in making another endeavor, for example the learning 'through' approach. In this manner, we contend that innovative character development can be encouraged utilizing a 'learning through' approach, where development of the association (and the authoritative personality) is done in parallel with the pioneering personality. Past research has demonstrated the association between the individual business visionary and the firm (for instance observe Bruyat and Julien, 2001; Fauchart and Gruber, 2011; Mugler, 1990), and expanding upon this we recommend that inside an activity based enterprise instruction, where learning through is the methodology utilized, the character development of the individual and the endeavor are frequently interlaced. The advancement of the 'narrative of the firm' is developed in parallel with the person's enterprising personality, in that both the individual job and the idea of the firm are arranged and legitimized through communication with 'noteworthy others, for example, key partners or investors. This interlaced personality development is to some degree, dependent on the learning through methodology of activity based business instruction, which utilizes the formation of a genuine endeavor as the learning vessel. There is have to examine further how activity based business enterprise training can and should bolster joint development of the individual character of the business visionary and the authoritative job of the endeavor being found.

Innovative character development requires further examination and talk. It is essential for both staff and understudies of business enterprise training to deliberately work with character development as understudies progress into a pioneering profession. Making a learning space (Kolb and Kolb, 2005), including time for individual and aggregate narrating and reflection, permits understudies, and encompassing partners, to understand encounters in connection to enterprising personality development. Recommended learning space settings as of now exist inside different activity based business trainings (Barr, Baker, Markham, and Kingon, 2009; Meyer, Aten, Krause, Metzger, and Holloway, 2011; Ollila and Williams Middleton, 2011; Rasmussen and Sørheim, 2006), however these settings have not explicitly been examined to investigate how enterprising character is developed in situ during understudy residency. For instance, extra research should be done to explore the manners by which the three parts of efficacious space (Sarasvathy, 2008), related with the basic leadership rationale of master business visionaries through the hypothesis of effectuation (Read, Wiltbank, and Sarasvathy, 2003; Sarasvathy, 2001), are or might be joined in the learning space of activity based enterprise training, and how this may affect character development (Nielsen and Lassen, 2012). These are standards regions for future research.

References

- i. Aaltio, I. (2008). *Management education as an identity construction: the case of Estonia and its transition economy background*. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 5(1), 83e99.
- ii. Anderson, A. R., & Warren, L. (2011). *The entrepreneur as hero and jester: enacting the entrepreneurial discourse*. *International Small Business Journal*, 29(6), 589e609.
- iii. Ashforth, B. E., & Mael, F. (1989). *Social identity theory and the organization*. *Academy of Management Review*, 14, 20e39.
- iv. Barr, S. H., Baker, T., Markham, S. K., & Kingon, A. I. (2009). *Bridging the valley of death: lessons learned from 14 years of commercialization of technology education*. *Academy of Management Learning and Education*, 8(3), 370e388.
- v. Barrett, F. J., & Peterson, R. (2000). *Appreciative learning cultures: developing competencies for global organizing*. *Organizational Development Journal*, 18(2), 10e21.
- vi. Baumol, W. J. (1986). *Entrepreneurship and a century of growth*. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 1(2), 141e145.
- vii. Baumol, W. J., Litan, R., & Schramm, C. (2007). *Good capitalism, bad capitalism, and the economics of growth and prosperity*. New Haven, CT: Yale University

- viii. Press.
- ix. Boje, D., & Smith, R. (2010). *Re-storying and visualizing the changing entrepreneurial identities of Bill Gates and Richard Branson*. *Culture & Organization*, 16(4), 307e331.
- x. Breslin, D., & Jones, C. (2012). *The evolution of entrepreneurial learning*. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 20, 3.
- xi. Bruyat, C., & Julien, P.-A. (2001). *Defining the field of research in entrepreneurship*. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 16(2), 165e180.
- xii. Chand, V. S., & Misra, S. (2009). *Teachers as educational-social entrepreneurs*. *Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 18(2), 219e228.
- xiii. Chandler, G., DeTienne, D., McKelvie, A., & Mumford, T. (2011). *Causation and effectuation processes: a validation study*. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 26, 375e390.
- xiv. Chang, J., & Rieple, A. (2013). *Assessing students' entrepreneurial skills development in live projects*. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 20(1), 225e241.
- xv. Clarke, J. (2011). *Revitalizing entrepreneurship: how visual symbols are used in entrepreneurial performances*. *Journal of Management Studies*, 48(6), 1365e1391.
- xvi. Co, M. J., & Mitchell, B. (2006). *Entrepreneurship education in South Africa: a nationwide survey*. *Education þ Training*, 48(5), 348e359.
- xvii. Collins, L., Smith, A., & Hannon, P. (2006). *Applying a synergistic learning approach in entrepreneurship education*. *Management Learning*, 37(3), 335e354.
- xviii. Cope, J. (2003). *Entrepreneurial learning and critical reflection: discontinuous events as triggers for 'higher-level' learning*. *Management Learning*, 34(4), 429e450.
- xix. Cope, J., & Watts, G. (2000). *Learning by doing: an exploration of experience, critical incidents and reflection in entrepreneurial learning*. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, 6(3), 104e124.
- xx. DeRue, D. S., & Ashford, S. J. (2010). *Who will lead and who will follow? A social process of leadership identity construction in organizations*. *Academy of Management Review*, 35(4), 627e653.
- xxi. Down, S., & Warren, L. (2008). *Constructing narratives of enterprise: cliches and entrepreneurial self-identity*. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, 14(1), 4e23.
- xxii. Essers, C., & Benschop, Y. (2007). *Enterprising identities: female entrepreneurs of Moroccan or Turkish origin in the Netherlands*. *Organization Studies*, 28(1), 49e69.
- xxiii. Falck, O., Heblich, S., & Luedemann, E. (2010). *Identity and entrepreneurship: do school peers shape entrepreneurial intentions?* *Small Business Economics*, 39(1), 39e59.
- xxiv. Fauchart, E., & Gruber, M. (2011). *Darwinians, communitarians, and missionaries: the role of founder identity in entrepreneurship*. *Academy of Management Journal*, 54(5), 935e957.
- xxv. Finkle, T. A., & Deeds, D. (2001). *Trends in the market for entrepreneurship faculty, 1989e1998*. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 16(6), 613e630.
- xxvi. Fletcher, D. E., & Watson, T. M. (2007). *Entrepreneurship, management learning and negotiated narratives: 'making it otherwise for us e otherwise for them'*. *Management Learning*, 38(1), 9e26.
- xxvii. Gibb, A. A. (1996). *Entrepreneurship and small business management: can we afford to neglect them in the twenty-first century business school?* *British Journal of Management*, 7(4), 309e321.
- xxviii. Gioia, D. A., Price, K., Hamilton, A. L., & Thomas, J. B. (2010). *Forging an identity: an insider-outsider study of processes involved in the formation of organizational identity*. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 55, 1e46.
- xxix. Gruber, M. (2007). *Uncovering the value of planning in new venture creation: a process and contingency perspective*. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 22(6), 782e807.
- xxx. Harmeling, S. S. (2011). *Re-storying an entrepreneurial identity: education, experience and self-narrative*. *Education þ Training*, 53(8/9), 741e749.
- xxxi. Harrison, R. T., & Leitch, C. M. (Eds.). (2011). *Entrepreneurial learning: Conceptual frameworks and applications*. London, UK: Routledge.

- xxxii. Heinonen, J. (2007). *An entrepreneurial-directed approach to teaching corporate entrepreneurship at university level*. *Education þ Training*, 49(4), 310e324.
- xxxiii. Heinonen, J., & Poikkijoki, S.-A. (2006). *An entrepreneurial-directed approach to entrepreneurship education: mission impossible?* *Journal of Management Development*, 25(1), 80e94.
- xxxiv. Honig, B. (2004). *Entrepreneurship education: toward a model of contingency-based business planning*. *Academy of Management Learning and Education*, 3(3), 258e273.
- xxxv. Honig, B., & Samuelsson, M. (2012). *Planning and the entrepreneur: a longitudinal examination of nascent entrepreneurs in Sweden*. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 50(3), 365e388.
- xxxvi. Hytti, U. (2003). *Stories of entrepreneurs: Narrative construction of identities*. Turku University.
- xxxvii. Hytti, U. (2005). *New meanings for entrepreneurs: from risk-taking heroes to safe-seeking professionals*. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 18(6), 594e611.
- xxxviii. Hytti, U., & O'Gorman, C. (2004). *What is "enterprise education"? An analysis of the objectives and methods of enterprise education programmes in four European countries*. *Education þ Training*, 46(1), 11e23.
- xxxix. Ibarra, H. (1999). *Provisional selves: experimenting with image and identity in professional adaptation*. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 44(4), 764e791.
- xl. Jain, S., George, G., & Maltarich, M. (2009). *Academics or entrepreneurs? Investigating role identity modification of university scientists involved in commercialization activity*. *Research Policy*, 38(6), 922e935.
- xli. Johansson, A. W. (2004). *Narrating the entrepreneur*. *International Small Business Journal*, 22(3), 273e293.
- xlii. Johannisson, B., Landström, H., & Rosenberg, J. (1998). *University training for entrepreneurship e an action frame of reference*. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 23(4), 477e496.
- xliiii. Jones, C., & Spicer, A. (2005). *The sublime object of entrepreneurship*. *Organization*, 12(2), 223e246.
- xliv. Karatas, -O€ zkan, M. (2011). *Understanding relational qualities of entrepreneurial learning: towards a multi-layered approach*. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 1e30.
- xlv. Karlsson, T., & Honig, B. (2007). *Norms surrounding business plans and their effect on entrepreneurial behavior*. *Frontiers of Entrepreneurship Research*, 27, 22. Article 1.
- xlvi. Katz, J. A. (2003). *The chronology and intellectual trajectory of American entrepreneurship education: 1876e1999*. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 18(2), 283e300.
- xlvii. Kirby, D. (2004). *Entrepreneurship education: can business schools meet the challenge?* *Education þ Training*, 46(8/9), 510e519.
- xlviii. Kolb, A. Y., & Kolb, D. (2005). *Learning styles and learning spaces: enhancing experiential learning in higher education*. *Academy of Management Learning and Education*, 4(2), 193e212.
- xlix. Lackeus, M. (2013). *Developing entrepreneurial competencies: An action-based approach and classification in education*. Licentiate. Chalmers University of Technology.
- l. Lounsbury, M., & Glynn, M. A. (2001). *Cultural entrepreneurship: stories, legitimacy, and the acquisition of resources*. *Strategic Management Journal*, 22, 545e564.
- li. Lundström, & Stevenson, L. (Eds.). (2002). *On the road to entrepreneurship*. FSF.
- lii. Madsen, M. T., Neergaard, H., & Ulhoi, J. P. (2008). *The influence of roles and identities on female entrepreneurial agency*. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 5(3e4), 358e372.
- liii. Martin, R. (1978). *Expert and referent power: a framework for understanding and maximizing consultation effectiveness*. *Journal of School Psychology*, 16(1), 49e55.
- liv. McMullan, W. E., & Long, W. A. (1987). *Entrepreneurship education in the nineties*. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 2(3), 261e275.
- lv. Meyer, A. D., Aten, K., Krause, A. J., Metzger, M. L., & Holloway, S. S. (2011). *Creating a university technology commercialisation programme: confronting conflicts between learning, discovery and commercialisation goals*. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation Management*, 13(2), 179e198.

- lvi. Morris, M. H., Kuratko, D. F., Schindehutte, M., & Spivack, A. J. (2012). Framing the entrepreneurial experience. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 36(1), 11e40.
- lvii. Mugler, J. (1990). *Entrepreneurship and the theory of the firm*. In R. Donckels, & A. Miettinen (Eds.), *New findings and perspectives in entrepreneurship* (pp. 3e15). Aldershot: Avebury.
- lviii. Mwasalwiba, E. S. (2010). Entrepreneurship education: a review of its objectives, teaching methods, and impact indicators. *Education þ Training*, 52(1), 20e47.
- lix. Nadin, S. (2007). Entrepreneurial identity in the care sector: navigating the contradictions. *Women in Management Review*, 22(6), 456e467.
- lx. Navis, C., & Glynn, M. A. (2011). Legitimate distinctiveness and the entrepreneurial identity: influence on investor judgments of new venture plausibility. *Academy of Management Review*, 36(3), 479e499.
- lxi. Nielsen, S., & Lassen, A. (2012). Identity in entrepreneurship effectuation theory: a supplementary framework. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 8(3), 373e389.
- lxii. Obrecht, J.-J. (2004). Entrepreneurial capabilities: a resource based systemic approach to international entrepreneurship. In L.-P. Dana (Ed.), *Handbook of research on international entrepreneurship* (pp. 248e264). Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar.
- lxiii. Obrecht, J.-J. (2011). On the relevance of the concept of entrepreneurial capabilities. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 13(2), 107e125.
- lxiv. Obschonka, M., Goethner, M., Silbereisen, R. K., & Cantner, U. (2012). Social identity and the transition to entrepreneurship: the role of group identification with workplace peers. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 80(1), 137e147.
- lxv. OECD. (2011). *Entrepreneurship at a Glance 2011*. London, UK: OECD Publishing.
- lxvi. Ollila, S., & Williams Middleton, K. (2011). The venture creation approach: integrating entrepreneurial education and incubation at the university. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation Management*, 13(2), 161e178.
- lxvii. Pittaway, L., & Cope, J. (2007). Simulating entrepreneurial learning: integrating experiential and collaborative approaches to learning. *Management Learning*, 38(2), 211e233.
- lxviii. Pittaway, L., & Edwards, C. (2012). Assessment: examining practice in entrepreneurship education. *Education þ Training*, 54(8), 778e800.
- lxix. Pittaway, L., & Thorpe, R. (2012). A framework for entrepreneurial learning: a tribute to Jason Cope. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 24(9e10), 837e859.
- lxx. Radu Lefebvre, M., & Redien-Collot, R. (2013). "How to do things with words": the discursive dimension of experiential learning in entrepreneurial mentoring dyads. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 51(3), 370e393.
- lxxi. Rae, D. (2000). Understanding entrepreneurial learning: a question of how? *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, 6(3), 145e159.
- lxxii. Rae, D. (2004). Entrepreneurial learning: a practical model from the creative industries. *Education þ Training*, 46(8/9), 492e500.
- lxxiii. Rae, D. (2005). Entrepreneurial learning: a narrative-based conceptual model. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 12(3), 323e335.
- lxxiv. Rae, D. (2006). Entrepreneurial learning: a conceptual framework for technology-based enterprise. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 18(1), 39e56.
- lxxv. Rasmussen, E., & Sørheim, R. (2006). Action-based entrepreneurship education. *Technovation*, 26(2), 185e194.
- lxxvi. Read, S., Wiltbank, R., & Sarasvathy, S. D. (2003). What do entrepreneurs really learn from experience? The difference between expert and novice entrepreneurs. In W. D. Bygrave (Ed.), *Frontiers of entrepreneurship research 2003*. Wellesley, MA: Babson College.
- lxxvii. Rigg, C., & O'Dwyer, B. (2012). Becoming an entrepreneur: researching the role of mentors in identity construction. *Education þ Training*, 54(4), 319e329.

- lxxviii. Sarasvathy, S. D. (2001). *Causation and effectuation: toward a theoretical shift from economic inevitability to entrepreneurial contingency*. *Academy of Management Review*, 26(2), 243e263.
- lxxix. Sarasvathy, S. D. (2008). *Effectuation: Elements of entrepreneurial expertise*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar.
- lxxx. Shepherd, D., & Haynie, J. M. (2009a/). *Birds of a feather don't always flock together: identity management in entrepreneurship*. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 24(4), 316e337.
- lxxxi. Shepherd, D., & Haynie, J. M. (2009b/). *Family business, identity conflict, and an expedited entrepreneurial process: a process of resolving identity conflict*. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 33(6), 1245e1264.
- lxxxii. Smith, R. (2011). *The role of storyboards and scrapbooks in propagating entrepreneurial value in family business settings*. *World Review of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development*, 7(3), 260e271.
- lxxxiii. Solomon, G. (2007). *An examination of entrepreneurship education in the United States*. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 14(2), 168e182.
- lxxxiv. Somers, M. R. (1994). *The narrative constitution of identity: a relational and network approach*. *Theory and Society*, 23(5), 605e649.
- lxxxv. Steyaert, C. (2007). *Of course that is not the whole (toy) story: entrepreneurship and the cat's cradle*. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 22(5), 733e751.
- lxxxvi. Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. M. (1990). *Basics of qualitative research: Grounded theory procedures and techniques*. Newbury Park, C.A: Sage Publications Ltd.
- lxxxvii. Stryker, S., & Serpe, R. (1982). *Commitment, identity salience and role behavior: theory and research example*. In W. Ickes, & E. S. Knowles (Eds.), *Personality, roles and social behavior* (pp. 199e218). New York, NY: Springer-Verlag.
- lxxxviii. Sveningsson, S., & Alvesson, M. (2003). *Managing managerial identities: organizational fragmentation, discourse and identity struggle*. *Human Relations*, 56(10), 1163e1193.
- lxxxix. Vinton, G., & Alcock, S. (2004). *Entrepreneurship in education*. *The International Journal of Education*, 18, 2/3.
- xc. Watson, T. J. (2009). *Entrepreneurial action, identity work and the use of multiple discursive resources*. *International Small Business Journal*, 27(3), 251e274. Wigren, C. (2003). *The spirit of Gnosjo. The grand narrative and beyond. Doctoral dissertation. Jo€nko€ping International Business School*.
- xc. Williams Middleton, K. (2013). *Becoming entrepreneurial: gaining legitimacy in the nascent phase*. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, 19(4), 404e424.
- xcii. Williams Middleton, K., & Donnellon, A. (2014). *Personalizing entrepreneurial learning: a pedagogy for facilitating the know why*. *Entrepreneurship Research Journal*, 4(2), 167e204.
- xciii. World Economic Forum. (2011). *Unlocking entrepreneurial capabilities to meet the global challenges of the 21st century: Final report on the entrepreneurship education workstream*. World Economic Forum Global Education Initiative. World Economic Forum.
- xciv. Wry, T., Lounsbury, M., & Glynn, M. A. (2011). *Legitimizing nascent collective identities: coordinating cultural entrepreneurship*. *Organization Science*, 22(2), 449e463.
- xcv. Yballe, L., & O'Connor, D. (2000). *Appreciative pedagogy: constructing positive models for learning*. *Journal of Management Education*, 24(4), 474e483.